

Original Research Article

Normal Umbilical Artery Doppler Assessment in Second and Third Trimester Singleton Gestation of Healthy Pregnant Women in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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Abstract

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Umbilical artery Doppler assessment is an important marker of uteroplacental insufficiency and consequent intrauterine growth restriction therefore assessment of normal values is key in early detection of these anomalies. This cohort study was carried out on 222 pregnant Nigerian women in a private hospital in Port Harcourt Nigeria. Duplex color Doppler sonography was utilized in measurement of Pulsatility Index (PI), Resistivity index (RI) and systolic/diastolic (S/D) ratio of the umbilical artery of fetuses during the 2nd and 3rd trimesters. The age range was from 20-45 years with a mean age of 28.3 ± 1.8 . The mean values and standard deviations (SD) of the PI and RI value of the umbilical artery in the 2nd and 3rd trimester were 1.05 (SD ± 0.24) and 0.63 (SD ± 0.10) respectively. In separate trimesters the mean value of PI in the 2nd trimester was 1.10 (SD ± 0.25), RI 0.6 (SD ± 0.12) and in the 3rd trimester PI 0.98 (SD ± 0.23), RI 0.5 (SD ± 0.07). There was significant difference between mean values of PI in different gestational ages ($t=3.76$, level of significance=0.000), PI value decreased with increasing gestational age ($r=-0.027$) but not statistically significant ($p=0.112$). Normal reference values of the umbilical artery doppler velocimetry in our environment has been documented and shows a normal variation of umbilical artery velocimetry in 2nd and 3rd trimester gestation with advancing gestational age.

Keywords: Doppler ultrasound, normal gestation, Umbilical artery

INTRODUCTION

Doppler ultrasonography of the umbilical circulation plays an important role in assessing the wellbeing of intrauterine gestation (Yash et al., 2016). Umbilical artery assessment is key in screening for maternal conditions like diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease, hypertension, prothrombotic states as well as fetal related conditions like suspected intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), previous pregnancy with IUGR, decreased fetal movement, oligohydramnios, and polyhydramnios (Berkley et al., 2012).

Intrauterine growth restriction is commonly defined as a fetal weight below the 10th percentile for gestational age which can be symmetric or asymmetric. IUGR has far

reaching consequences during pregnancy, delivery and after birth of the fetus with social problems both to the child and mother (Nagar et al., 1993). The likelihood of perinatal and maternal mortality is increased with preeclampsia regardless of advances in antenatal care. Studies have shown that mortality rate of growth retarded infants is 3–8 times higher than in normal weight newborns. Disturbances of development and adaptation are common in live born growth retarded infants than normal weight babies (Campbell and Soothill, 1993). Studies have revealed that majority of deaths in IUGR fetuses can be prevented if IUGR is diagnosed by 34 weeks (McIntire et al., 1999; Fawole et al., 2011;

Maulik and Figueroa, 2005). A study by Wladimiroff et al. (1987) showed significant reduction in labor induction, caesarean section for fetal distress and neurologic injuries when doppler velocimetry was included in surveillance of high-risk pregnancies. Therefore, assessment of the umbilical artery circulation is essential in better clinical management of pathological pregnancies.

Ultrasonography has become the foremost investigation of choice in assessment of high-risk pregnancies. Ultrasound scan is readily available, accessible and cost effective with little or no side effects to the mother and fetuses. The umbilical artery (UA) indices are calculated by measuring the blood flow waveforms through portions of the floating umbilical cord in Doppler studies. The 2nd and 3rd trimester gestations are more reliable ages to measure the UA indices as they show an increased resistance to flow as opposed to 1st trimester gestations where the diastolic flow is not fully detected with umbilical doppler waveform analysis showing absence of end-diastolic flow (Maulik and Figueroa, 2005).

The peak systolic volume (PSV), end diastolic volume (EDV), systolic diastolic ratio (S/D ratio), pulsatility index of gosling (PI) and the resistivity index of pucelot (RI) are the Doppler umbilical artery indices used in assessing normal gestation (Gosling et al., 1971; Pourcelot, 1974). In cases of preeclampsia and IUGR there is an increased impedance to flow resulting in an increased PI and RI due to reduced placental perfusion and utero placental insufficiency.

Despite various studies in the developed countries there have been no definite values for doppler velocimetric parameters for umbilical arteries at the second and third trimesters in our environment. Due to the current advancement, the reference values being used are those of the western population therefore to establish a normal reference value for the normal PI and RI in a Nigerian population this present study was carried out in Port Harcourt.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a prospective longitudinal study of two hundred and twenty-two healthy pregnant women with ages between 20 and 45 years conducted in a private hospital in Port Harcourt for a period of one year.

Demographic data were taken, and gestational age was determined by the date of the last menstrual period and/or measurement by ultrasound scan. Subjects were selected with gestational ages between 2nd (13-26 weeks) and 3rd (27-40 weeks) trimester, had singleton pregnancies without any fetal anomaly, no diabetes, hypertension or any acquired illness. Subjects underwent duplex color doppler scanning of the fetal umbilical artery after appropriate consent.

All examinations were performed independently by the authors with a Logic 2 ultrasound machine (General Electric; Austria) with a convex transducer of 3-5MHZ frequency. Subjects were scanned in the decubitus position at a 15-30° achieved by angulation of the couch and a head rest.

Ultrasound gel was applied on the transducer and the umbilical cord was identified on B mode ultrasonography. Doppler images were acquired using pulsed Doppler in the absence of fetal movement. Measurements of the umbilical arteries were performed, with an isonation angle of < 60°, sample volumes of 1-2 mm at the central portions of the vessel and spectral peak average intensities of 100m/wcm². The Peak systolic velocity (PSV), End diastolic volume (EDV), Pulsatility index (PI), resistivity index (RI) and systolic/diastolic ratio (SD ratio) were obtained for the umbilical artery wave form from at least four consecutive wave forms.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed with statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 (IBM) The mean and standard deviation of the doppler indices were recorded for descriptive analysis. Student's t- test was used to determine the difference between doppler parameters in the second and third trimesters and Pearson correlation used to determine the correlation between doppler parameters and gestational age.

RESULTS

A total of two hundred and twenty-two pregnant women who met the inclusion criteria were scanned during the study period. The ages ranged from 20-45 years with a mean age of 28.3 ± 1.8 years. The mean and standard deviation for the gestational age in weeks in the different trimesters were 21.45 ± 1.53 and 25.98 ± 1.21 for second trimester and third trimester gestation, respectively. There were one hundred and eight (108) subjects in the second trimester (48.6%) and one hundred and fourteen (114) subjects in the third trimester (51.4%). Table 1.

The maximum value of PI was 1.80 and minimum value was 0.64 for both second and third trimesters with a mean of 1.05 ± 0.24. The PI in the second trimester showed values of 0.68 to 1.80 with a mean of 1.10 ± 0.25 while that of the third trimester showed values of 0.64 to 1.76 with a mean of PI 0.98 ± 0.23. Students sample t test showed values of t 3.761 with p 0.000

The maximum value of RI was 0.96 and minimum value was 0.40 for both second and third trimesters with a mean of 0.63 ± 0.10. RI in the second trimester showed values of 0.4-0.96 with a mean of 0.6 SD ± 0.12 while that of the third trimester showed values of 0.4 to 0.80

Table 1. Maternal Age and gestational age of subjects

Age (years)	Second Trimester(n)	Third trimester(n)	Total (%)
20-24 years	16(7.2%)	11(4.95%)	27(12.2%)
25-29 years	38(17.1%)	43(19.3%)	81(36.5%)
30-34 years	42(18.9%)	34(15.3%)	76(34.3%)
35-40 years	9 (4.0%)	21(9.45%)	30(13.5%)
40- 44 years	3 (1.35%)	5(2.25%)	8(3.6%)
Total	108(48.6%)	114(51.4%)	222(100%)

Table 2. Umbilical artery Doppler indices at second and third trimester gestation

Variables	Second trimester(mean)	Third trimester(mean)	t	P
PSV (cm)	33.06 ±11.92	35.79 ± 10.0	-4.845	0.005
EDV (cm)	13.41 ± 5.23	16.34 ± 4.42	-5.674	0.003
S/D ratio	2.71 ± 0.54	2.52 ± 0.34	3.913	0.005
RI	0.6 ± 0.12	0.5 ± 0.07	4.302	0.003
PI	1.10 ± 0.25	0.98 ± 0.23	6.543	0.000

PSV - peak systolic velocity; EDV- end diastolic volume; S/D- systolic to diastolic ratio, RI resistivity index, PI-pulsatility index, p <0.05

Table 3. Correlation of maternal age and gestational age of subjects with umbilical artery doppler parameters in second and third trimester

Variables	PSV r (p)	EDV r (p)	S/D ratio r (p)	RI r (p)	PI r (p)
Maternal age	0.125(0.234)	0.318(0.046)	0.023(0.031)	0.062(0.007)	0.019(0.011)
13-26 weeks	0.012(0.082)	0.051(0.009)	0.034(0.128)	0.022(0.013)	0.076(0.327)
27-40 weeks	0.056(0.014)	0.006(0.053)	0.054(0.034)	0.015(0.037)	0.043(0.036)

PSV - peak systolic velocity; EDV- end diastolic volume; S/D- systolic to diastolic ratio, RI resistivity index, PI- pulsatility index p <0.05

with a mean of 0.5 SD ± 0.07. t test showed values of t 4.30 with p Of 0.066

The Peak systolic volume (PSV) mean in the second trimester was 33.06 ± 11.92 and third trimester was 35.79 ± 10.0. End diastolic volumes (EDV) means were 13.41 ± 5.23 and 10.1 ± 3.54 in the second trimester and third trimesters. Systolic/ diastolic ratio (S/D ratio) mean in the second trimester was 2.7 ± 0.54 and the mean in the third trimester was 2.52 ± 0.34. Table 2.

There was no significant correlation between the umbilical artery parameters and the gestational age in the second and third trimesters.

DISCUSSION

Doppler indices in the second and third trimester gestation are non-invasive methods of assessing fetal and uteroplacental circulation to rule out high risk pregnancies (Nagar et al., 1993; Newnham et al., 1991; Campbell et al., 1986). Normal reference range of umbilical Doppler velocimetry has been described by Bhide et al. (2013) and other researchers in other climes.

Normal values in our environment help establish basis for a high index of suspicion in abnormal pregnancies as abnormal values of umbilical artery have been documented in previous studies (Baschat, 2004). The study documented the normal mean values of the umbilical doppler velocimetry in healthy pregnant women with singleton gestation in the second and third trimesters. This underscores the importance of the early detection of IUGR for appropriate early diagnosis and therapy.

The Doppler indices included the PSV, EDV, S/D ratio, RI and PI. The PSV and EDV showed a progressive increase while the S/D ratio, RI and PI showed a gradual reduction as the gestational age increased. These findings agree with the fact that there is a decrease in the vascular resistance in the fetal and uteroplacental circulation with advancing gestation. Studies by (Acharya et al., 2005; Kurmanavicius et al., 1997; Ayoola et al., 2016; Awowole et al., 2019) showed similar decrease in the S/D ratio, RI and PI.

The mean peak systolic volume value of the umbilical artery in the second trimester was 33.06 ± 11.92 and 35.79 ± 10.0 in the third trimester. This was like a study

by Acharya et al but slightly differed from Adekanmi et al. (2017) who had higher values of 39.39 ± 8.90 and 43.85 ± 8.73 in both trimesters. However, the studies both showed an increase in the PSV as gestational age increased. Owen et al., (2003); Ferdousi et al., (2013) and Akiyama et al. (1999) also showed an increase in the PSV as the gestational age increased

The PI is the difference between maximum and minimum blood flow velocities in the umbilical artery. It is a good marker of placental insufficiency. The mean PI in the study was 1.10 ± 0.25 and 0.98 ± 2.3 in the second and third trimesters respectively which showed a gradual decrease with increasing gestational age. This finding corroborated those of Adekanmi et al. (2017) 1.0 ± 2.0 but was lower than the values from Ferdousi et al. (2013; Akiyama et al., 1999) 1.18 ± 0.25 and 1.33 ± 0.29 , respectively. Similarly, the RI showed a gradual decline like the PI from the second to the third trimester with mean values similar to studies done in Ibadan, Nigeria 0.60 ± 0.11 and 0.53 ± 0.11 . This present study observed that the value of RI in the second trimester 0.6 ± 0.12 decreased in the third trimester 0.50 ± 0.7 also in accordance with the study carried out by Srikumar et al. (2017) in India.

CONCLUSION

The study has established preliminary reference values for the umbilical artery pulsatility and resistivity indexes in healthy pregnant women in Port Harcourt. The findings correlate with normal variation of the umbilical artery in 2nd and 3rd trimester gestation

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